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**Strengths, weaknesses and
opportunities of machine learning
in the field of oncology**

BY

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Chapter One

1. Introduction

Over the last two decades, it is noticed that machine learning and its applications has been progressively spreading in almost every sector in the world whether it is technology, retail industries, education, agricultural, businesses or healthcare (Nardini, 2020). Machine learning has the ability to solve extremely complex problems without being explicitly programmed just by using mathematical, statistical and probabilistic models and the models learn from a huge collection of historical data. Machine learning has become a very sensitive matter when it comes to the healthcare system because it is linked to the life of humans. Applications of machine learning have started performing better and faster jobs than humans in healthcare sectors such as identification and diagnosis of diseases, predictive approach to treatment, collection of patients data, robotic surgery, drug discovery and production etc ().

Oncology is the field of medicine to help in treatment of cancer by surgical, radiation and medical oncology where surgery operations involve treating cancer, radiation therapy for treatment of cancer and using chemotherapy drugs respectively (cancer.org, na). However, ML applications are used in all the treatment processes. Machine learning applications could be increasing their accuracy in predicting survival of a cancer patient. The accuracy of the ML model has seen significant improvement every year and it is around 15% to 20% increment in the accuracy from the last year (Kourou et al, 2015).

Knowing the importance of the study, strengths of ML applications are discussed where various models with datasets and its visualization along with weaknesses and opportunities are also mentioned.

1.1 Aims and Objective

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1.1.1 Aim

The main aim of this research is to point out strengths, weaknesses and the opportunities of machine learning in the oncology field.

1.1.2 Objective

The objectives of this study is mentioned as points in the following:

1. Critical evaluation of earlier and relevant published research papers on machine learning, oncology and similar literature.
2. Collection of data from the survey and relevant sources.
3. To analyze and visualize on the basis of gathered data to observe insight, result and recognize the strength, weakness and opportunities for machine learning in the field of oncology.
4. Research findings comparison with the relevant published papers.
5. Programming language for the machine learning
- 6.

1.2 Research Question / Hypothesis

RQ1. What are the appropriate research methods available for the diagnosis of various types of cancer?

RQ2. What are the advantages and limitations for the used methods?

RQ3. What were the accuracy of the methods?

1.3 Approach

An interpretivist qualitative approach will be followed for this research project. The main kind for this study is a case study is been held using a questionnaire and interviews techniques. Furthermore information is discussed in chapter 3 where rationale is selected for this approach.

1.6 Summary

This chapter has outlined the main structure for the research topic. A background about the topic was highlighted in terms of neuroscience and spreadsheets errors in addition to the motivation behind choosing it. The aim, objectives and research questions has been also clarified and set. The approach that will be used also was briefly discussed. The first a step toward this research was taken.

Chapter Two

2. Literature Review

In this section, information and discussions are provided in a sequential and logical manner so that it could lead to understanding the background of this study.

2.1 Overview of Machine Learning

2.1.1 Definition, types and its benefits

Machine learning (ML) is a mathematical technique that enables computers to learn from big data without being traditionally programmed (Samuel, 1988). ML models improve their performance automatically by the past experiences (Mitchell, 1997). There is no difference between ML model and statistics. Almost every model in machine learning is based on statistics, for instance $y = mx + c$ is a linear equation or equation of line where c is intercept or constant and m is slope of a line and this shows a statistical graph shown in the figure 1. Similarly, in machine learning, $h_{\theta}(x) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 x$ is the linear regression with one variable where x and $h_{\theta}(x)$ are independent and dependent variables respectively. θ_0 and θ_1 are parameters which are then used to minimize the cost function. Cost function is basically the error between actual and predicted point. Different lines will be formed on different parameters. For example, if $\theta_0 = 0$ and $\theta_1 = 1$ then a straight line appears which will pass through the coordinates $(0, 0)$. If $\theta_0 = 2$ and $\theta_1 = 0$ then a straight line will cross the y -axis at $(0, 2)$. And if $\theta_0 = 1$ and $\theta_1 = 2$ then the straight line will be totally different from the above examples. The graphs are mentioned in **figure 2** to understand the examples better.

There are several examples of machine learning such as ranking the web pages in google search engine, categorizing news articles according to their tags, email spam filtering where ML separates the necessary emails from spam email, identifying diseases and recommending appropriate drugs, etc.

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Basically, there are three types of machine learning: supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement. These are discussed in detail in the following.

1. **Supervised learning:** In supervised learning, models are trained by using labeled data where users feed the known data into the model to get trained however the known data have input, output and both have labeled on it as it can be seen in the figure 3. Once the model is trained, the model is asked to give desired output and the model is able to generate accurate output. Accuracy of the model depends on various factors but out of them, the most important factor is the number of input data. If the input data is huge, the accuracy of the model will be more.

Figure 3 Supervised learning model example

Two types of problems can be solved by supervised learning which are regression and classification. In the regression problem, the results are generated from continuous output however in classification problems, the results are predicted from discrete output.

2. **Unsupervised learning:** In unsupervised learning, models are trained by using unlabelled data where users feed the unknown data into the model to get trained. For example, a new born baby does not know anything neither language nor things therefore a new born baby can act as an unsupervised model. He started learning language, differentiating between men and women, car, dog, horse, cat and grasping more things day by day by getting input from people, animals, their behaviors, Tv, and music. Similarly, unsupervised models that take unknown data and learn by themselves are mentioned in figure 4. In this, models try to acquire the similar patterns by themselves by making different clusters. These types of algorithms are more complex compared to supervised learning and they solve more complex problems than supervised algorithms. Clustering, neural network, anomaly detection, etc (Johnson, 2022).

Figure 4 Unsupervised learning model

3. Reinforcement learning: In reinforcement learning, models are trained by trial, error feedback and experiences. It is based on reward and policy. In this, there is an agent who performs an action in the environment and gets reward or penalty on the basis of action. State has been changed while performing action therefore the agent makes a policy on the basis of the changed state. Now the next time, the agent will perform according to the changed state shown in figure 5. This way unsupervised learning models learn.

Figure 5 Reinforcement learning Model

2.1.2 Deep learning

Deep learning (DL) is the subset of machine learning and artificial intelligence that deals with huge neural networks (NN) and making models so that it could solve most complex problems and produce accurate data driven decisions (Kelleher, 2019). DL is most suited for complex problems and big data such as speech recognition, face recognition and face detection. Every deep learning algorithm uses neural networks where a bunch of various types of neurons are

strongly connected together shown in the following figure 6, the same as a network of neurons connected complexly in a human's brain.

Figure 6 neural network

Neurons is a computational unit where it receives a number of inputs through input link and calculates mathematical work or computation in order to get an accurate output. There are three layers: input, hidden and output layers. Input layer is the first layer in a neural network where artificial neurons ($x1, x2, x3$) have some initial values to process further. Hidden layer in the neural network is the main computational layer where a high level of mathematics work is done by each neuron ($a1, a2, a3, a4, a12\dots a15$) in order to get accurate results and pass to the output layer. Last layer in NN is known as the output layer which produces the final outputs. Logistic function or sigmoid function are used to make a simple NN model given in the following formula 1.

$$g(z) = 1 / (1 + e^{-z})$$

$$h_{\theta}(x) = 1 / (1 + e^{-\theta x})$$

Where θ and x are the parameter vectors.

The benefit of having machine learning is that it can solve advanced and complex problems faster than any human can think of. ML can do almost everything without the intervention of any human being from prediction, recommendation, weather forecasting, driving to teaching and selling. Therefore, it is said that ML is one of the most powerful tools in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

2.2 Oncology

2.2.1 Overview

Oncology is the combination of two words i.e “onco” and “logy” however it is taken from greek word *ὄγκος* which means “*tumors*” or in another word “*cancer*” and “*logy*” means study which cumulatively means study of cancer. It is the branch of medicine which deals with treatment, diagnosis of tumors and early detection of cancers (Menna, 2022). Those who practice in the field of oncology in order to treat people with cancer are known as oncologists (Wikipedia, na). The treatment of cancer includes medical oncology, radiation oncology and surgical oncology (Menna, 2022).

1. Medical Oncology (MO): It is the process in which medicines are focused in the treatment or diagnosis of cancers or tumors. Medicines involved such as chemotherapy, immunotherapy and hormone therapy (Laguaite, 2020). Chemotherapy medicines are very powerful or contain powerful chemicals that are used to destroy the abnormally fast growing cells or in another word cancer cells in the body (mayoclinic, 2022). Immunotherapy uses substances made from living organisms which deal with treatment of cancer by boosting the immune system (IS) in the body. Boosted IS by immunotherapy used to fight against cancer cells, infections and other diseases (cancer.org, na). However, hormone therapy is also a treatment process for cancer where it stops or slows down the fast growing cells in the body.
2. Radiation oncology (RO): It is the study of medicines that deals with radiation therapy (RA) to treat cancer. RA is also the most common method to treat cancer where high energy waves or particles such as x-rays, gamma rays, electrons or protons are practiced in order to kill the abnormally growing cells (cancer.org, na).
3. Surgical oncology (SO): It is the study of surgery to treat cancer. In this treatment process, tumors of cancers or portions of body parts where cancer cells coming out are taken or cut out from the patient's body using an operation. There are two types of surgery in oncology given in the following.
 - Open surgery: In this type of surgery, all or parts of tumors are removed.
 - Minimal Invasive surgery: In this type of surgery, there are four methods: laparoscopy where a cancer surgeon inserts laparoscopy (a tube with camera attached) in the patient's body for small incision, laser surgery in which a surgeon

use a high intensity beam light to remove the cancer tumors, cryosurgery in which the use of nitrogen liquid to freeze cancer cells, and the last method is robotic surgery where a surgeon use robotic tools instead of using hand to hold surgical tools (Markman, 2022).

2.3 Common ML methods used in Oncology for the treatment of cancer

In the field of oncology, various tools and technologies have been used for decades. The most advanced technology used in oncology to treat cancer is AI, ML and DL where Oncologists collect data and feed into the machine learning model in order to detect, recommend the medicines, diagnose, predict the cancers and many more. In this section, ML methods are grabbed from already published research papers which show the treatment of various cancers. Clinical and imaging data are considered in order to get an accurate screening strategy. As an instance, various ML applications have been developed for breast cancer to estimate the risk of a patient and have seen better performances. Hybrid DL, a deep learning model is developed for full field mammograms to assess risk for breast cancer and found out to be more accurate around 0.70 AUC (area under the receiver operating characteristic curve) compared to other model such as Tyrer-Cuzick model (TC) which had 0.62 AUC (Yala et al, 2019).

$$Accuracy = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$$

$$Specificity = TN / (TN + FP)$$

$$Sensitivity = TP / (TP + FN)$$

Study of ML in prostate cancer has been done where an multi parameterized artificial neural network(ANN) model with 2 hidden layers and each layer had 12 neurons is created for the prediction of cancer risk. The results came up with 91% specificity on the training set and 89.4% specificity on the validation set however, sensitivity for the prediction of prostate cancer was low in both the cases training (21.5%) as well as validation (23.2%) set (Roffman, 2018).

Moreover, machine learning tools are being used for risk prediction for lung and pancreas where no screening strategies are available as of now. Hart and his colleague in their study on “A multi-parameterized artificial neural network for lung cancer risk prediction” developed an ANN multi-parameterized model for the risk of lung and pancreas cancer where the results showed that model got sensitivity = 79.8% and specificity = 79.9% in the training set. However, sensitivity = 75.3% and specificity = 80.6% in the validation set. Further, the same number of data is also used in support vector machine (SVM) and random forest to predict both models have performed better than ANN in terms of sensitivity and specificity on training set, however ANN performed better on validation set (Hart, 2018).

2.4 Strength and weaknesses of ML methods used in Oncology

2.4.1 Strength and weakness

There are different methods of machine learning used in treating cancers based on the accuracy of the model. In the case of breast cancer, convolutional neural network (CNN) is applied to classify the area of mammograms from the high resolution images. CNN makes easy and time saving for classification of mammograms from the image to get most accurate results (Nemade, 2022).

Feature selection from thousands of features is one of the most important methods in machine learning because there are huge number of feature presents in cancer data and it needs to use only those features which are important for the model and the methods such as random forest, SVM, KNN performs better in feature selection along with convolutional neural networks using minimum processing time and it is fast in performance (Kooi, 2022).

2.5 Risk assessment

It is the process of identifying accurate high risk patients that is most important in order to organize the screening program. In these events, a huge amount of data or information of patients because it would be easy for machine learning models to develop cost effective tools.

Chapter Three

3 Research methodology

In this part, research methodology is described in different stages in order to develop research strategy using research onion. Research onion represents the tree of research methodology. Every stage in this methodology explains in detail about the process of research such as what to choose for the research, in what ways and what options we have. All the stages are ordered sequentially and shown in an onion shaped figure 7 which is designed and explained by Mark saunders. Those stages are philosophy, approach, methodological choice, strategies, time horizon, and techniques for data collection and analysis.

Figure 7 Research onion as found in Saunders et al. (2009, p.108)

3.1 Philosophy

Philosophy is the top layer in the framework of research methodology where it describes the set of beliefs that how the data collection and data analysis will be done in the research.

3.1.1 Positivism

Positivism means certainty, confidence, trust or faith. For example muslims are absolutely certain that there is only one God. Positivism says every concept can be quantified or exact results can be calculated from the research. It is a philosophical system which can be scientifically verified and mathematically proof therefore it refuses metaphysics and theism. It is

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based on a conclusion which can be verified and not based on purely intuition. Positivism's followers or positivists have beliefs on the objective reality that is based on data rather than believing on sixth sense. In this, research is organized in a structured manner and based on quantitative research so that every process is crystal clear. Positivism is based on facts, quantitative, experimental, comparative analysis, observation deduction and objectivity. Those who follow positivism we call Positivist.

The principles of positivism are as follows.

1. There should be no difference between social and natural in terms of logic.
2. Explanation and prediction should be the aim of the research.
3. Humans should sense or observe empirically to the research.
4. Science is not based on common sense rather than logical and mathematical proof.
5. Science should be judged by only logic.

3.1.2 Interpretivism

Interpretivism is an approach of interpreting things subjectively where it contains its own opinions and explains according to its own perspective. It does not follow reality, opposes positivism and considers subjectivity is a reality. Result findings in the interpretivism are its own meaning not from any external source and based on qualitative data. It is also known as Anti-Positivism. According to these methodologies, every individual is different from others. Its basic principles are mentioned in the following.

1. Social science methodologies are not equal to natural science and both the methodologies should be totally different or separate from each other.

$$SS \neq NS$$

2. It identifies belief and reason because it leads to action.
3. It follows and researches subjective data.

Let's take a real example: There is a political agenda going on between Muslims and Hindu in India. News channel establishes panels of specialists/experts for debate that talk on the topics. Some Hindu and Muslims experts put their own views without the objective data and analysis. They explain their views on the basis of their religious belief, emotions and their agenda specially BJP leaders talk without facts and proof and main aim of their agenda is to continue fight between muslims and Hindus in india. Therefore, in this example BJP follows interpretivism methodologies and the BJP leaders became interpretivist.

3.1.3 Realism

Realism is an approach where one has an idea that is far from reality. It depends on assumption and one can assume anything and that could lead to development of knowledge. For example, if

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one can think that there is no existence of the country Switzerland but the reality is there is an existence of Switzerland. Object is independent of one's mind. We call this realism.

3.2 Approach

3.2.1 Inductive

Inductive research is such a study that begins with observations and the end results of the study is the theory. In this approach, theories are made on the basis of observations, interviews are conducted, and different qualitative methods but not on hypotheses. It is less structured because a small amount of data is used and available openly such as interviews and observations are easily conducted and data can be easily modified.

3.2.2 Deductive

Deductive results is such study that begins with making an hypothesis and the end results of the study will be confirmation or rejection. In this approach, Confirmation and rejection is based on different research questions and their hypothesis. Quantitative techniques are mostly used in this approach. It is a highly structured approach because there is a specific aim where a large amount of data is used to link specifically with hypotheses and confirm or reject on the basis of data.

3.2.3 Discussion and rationale for choice of approach

Researchers have used both inductive and deductive but those researchers who use unstructured and less amount of data follow a deductive approach. But an Inductive approach is chosen in this study because it is structured and millions of data are used for the hypothesis in order to get accurate results.

3.3 Strategies

There are four types of strategies mentioned in the onion methodologies of research which are archival, survey, case study and action. Since an inductive approach is chosen for this study therefore, case study reflects for this research.

3.3.1 Case Study

Case study is the process of research or empirical investigation where it is conducted on a specific object/individual/organization so that a clear life situation and solution could be found

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out using multiple methods of data collection (Robson, 2002). In this approach, quantitative data and qualitative data can be collected and further used for analysis and interpretation.

3.2.2 Discussion and rationale for choice of case study

Study of machine learning methods in the field of oncology is a complex field and most important because it is linked with the life of humans. The case study of ML models which are used for breast cancer, prostate cancer and lungs and pancreas where risk factor and accuracy are explored.

In the case of this research, complex fields that are machine learning and oncology (a field of medicines) are selected. Various ML models such as CNN, SVM, ANN and hybrid DL that have worked more accurately on finding risk factors are selected from already published journals.

3.4 Choices

Quantitative research is chosen in this study as a positivism inductive case.

3.5 Time Horizon

There are two types of time horizon: 1. Cross-sectional 2. Longitudinal.

When the time is limited, the problem is urgent and studies have to be finished within a specific time period known as cross-sectional. However, in longitudinal there is no time restriction for the study and data collection.

3.5.1 Discussion and rationale for choice of case study

In this research, there was time restriction for the study to complete and data collected within time limited. Therefore, Cross-sectional time horizon is chosen for this study.

3.6 Data Collection and Data Analysis

According to (Morgan, 2001) in his study of “Data collection techniques” data can be collected through any techniques as research approaches are designed orthogonal to the techniques. Data collection and data analysis totally depends on the research methodologies (Bryman, 2012). It is the process of selecting the types of data and techniques for the data collection.

In the case of this study, data will be collected through interviews and questionnaires.

3.7 Conclusion

This chapter is to figure out about methodologies facets and used to conduct the study. Inductive is applied for approach and the selected philosophy is an interpretivist. To address the topics, a specific case study is chosen and questionnaire interviews make the study qualitative. Cross sectional will be the time horizon.

4 Gantt Chart and Project Plan

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